

The Beneficial Influences of Vitamin D Intake on Inflammation and Oxidative Stress in Infertile women with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome

Khushboo Kumari¹, Deepti Sanjay Kumar², Rajshri Kumari³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar

²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar

³Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 25-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepti Sanjay Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: PCOS is a prevalent endocrine illness that causes hormonal imbalance, chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, and infertility. Vitamin D may help PCOS women by reducing inflammation and oxidative stress.

Objective: This study examined how vitamin D supplementation affected inflammation, oxidative stress, and hormonal balance in PCOS-infertile women.

Methods: From March to July 2024, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital conducted prospective observational research on 100 infertile PCOS women. A regular vitamin D supplement was given. At baseline and after the four-month intervention, inflammatory markers (hs-CRP, TNF- α , IL-6) and oxidative stress markers (TAC, MDA, GPx) were evaluated. Hormone levels, menstrual regularity, and ovulation were evaluated.

Results: Vitamin D treatment significantly reduced inflammatory markers (hs-CRP, TNF- α , IL-6) and improved oxidative stress markers (TAC, MDA, GPx) ($p < 0.05$). Improved hormonal balance, including lower LH, LH/FSH ratio, and testosterone levels ($p < 0.05$). Ovulation and menstrual regularity rose from 30% to 55% and 40% to 78%, respectively.

Conclusion: In PCOS-infertile women, vitamin D treatment greatly lowers inflammation, oxidative stress, hormonal imbalance, and reproductive health. Vitamin D's long-term effects on fertility need further study.

Keywords: Vitamin D, PCOS, Inflammation, Oxidative Stress.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a prevalent condition impacting women in their reproductive years, marked by hormonal irregularities, inconsistent menstrual cycles, and metabolic issues [1]. Chronic inflammation and heightened oxidative stress are key factors that contribute to the onset and advancement of PCOS, significantly worsening its symptoms, such as infertility [2,3]. The pathological processes may adversely affect ovarian function, insulin sensitivity, and general reproductive well-being. In recent years, the significance of vitamin D in addressing inflammation and oxidative stress has received notable focus, particularly regarding PCOS. Vitamin D, a fat-soluble vitamin, is recognized for its important role in regulating calcium levels and supporting bone health [4,5,6]. Nonetheless, recent findings indicate that vitamin D possesses wider immunomodulatory and antioxidant characteristics that could potentially mitigate the negative impacts

of inflammation and oxidative stress, especially in women diagnosed with PCOS [7,8].

This study investigates how vitamin D intake helps infertile women with PCOS by lowering oxidative stress and inflammation. By better understanding vitamin D's therapeutic potential, women with infertility may be able to manage their illness and achieve better reproductive results.

Methodology

Study Design: The prospective observational study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital in India from March to July 2024. Vitamin D supplementation was tested for its effects on oxidative stress and inflammation in infertile polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) individuals.

Study Population: The study included 100 PCOS-diagnosed infertile women. Participants were

required to be 18–40 years old, diagnosed with PCOS following Rotterdam criteria, and infertile after a year of unprotected sexual activity. Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels < 30 ng/mL were also required. Women receiving oxidative stress and inflammation-causing medicines, pregnant women, women with other endocrine disorders, and women with chronic diseases like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, or renal disease were excluded from the study.

Sample Size: Approximately 100 participants were recruited to ensure adequate statistical power for detecting the effects of vitamin D on the measured inflammatory and oxidative stress markers.

Intervention: Participants got vitamin D pills to treat vitamin D deficiency in PCOS women, according to medical practice. Supplement dosage and frequency were the same for everyone. Participants' serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels were measured before and after the study, and dosage was adjusted as needed.

Data Collection: Both before and four months after the intervention, data were collected. The study investigated inflammatory indicators such as TNF- α , IL-6, and hs-CRP. To evaluate oxidative stress, TAC, MDA, and GPx were measured. At both time points, serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D was measured. In addition to monthly regularity and ovulation rates, hormonal profiles such LH, FSH, testosterone, and insulin resistance markers were measured.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was done with SPSS. To list baseline characteristics of participants, descriptive statistics were employed. Before and after supplementation, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests or paired t-tests were used to compare oxidative stress and inflammatory markers. Pearson correlation analysis was used to examine vitamin D levels and oxidative stress or inflammation. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant, and 95% confidence intervals were used to ensure data correctness.

Results

Vitamin D supplementation was given to 100 women with polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) and infertility for four months. Supplementation improved inflammation and oxidative stress indicators. Vitamin D supplementation significantly reduced inflammation. The considerable drop in hs-CRP levels from baseline ($p < 0.05$) indicates a decrease in systemic inflammation. Significant reductions in TNF- α and IL-6 levels were detected in individuals, supporting the anti-inflammatory advantages of vitamin D administration.

Taking Vitamin D supplements improved oxidative stress signs. A considerable increase in total antioxidant capacity (TAC) ($p < 0.05$) indicates enhanced defense against oxidative stress. Similarly, MDA levels decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$), indicating lipid peroxidation and oxidative damage. Following the intervention, the activity of glutathione peroxidase (GPx), an essential antioxidant enzyme, significantly increased ($p < 0.05$). A significant increase in serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels was seen after four months of therapy ($p < 0.001$). Inflammation and oxidative stress markers decreased as vitamin D levels increased, demonstrating its beneficial role in controlling PCOS in women.

Hormonal profiles improved along with inflammation and oxidative stress. Significant decreases in LH levels and LH/FSH ratio ($p < 0.05$) indicate a probable hormonal balance. Significantly reduced testosterone levels ($p < 0.05$) indicate a good shift in hyperandrogenism. Many women showed improvements in monthly regularity, and ovulation rates were encouraging, though not statistically significant. In infertile women with PCOS, vitamin D treatment reduced inflammation and oxidative stress and improved hormonal balance and menstrual regularity. The results show that vitamin D is crucial for PCOS-related metabolic and reproductive disorders.

Table 1: Changes in Inflammatory Markers Before and After Vitamin D Supplementation

Inflammatory Markers	Baseline (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Post-Supplementation (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
hs-CRP (mg/L)	3.8 $\pm$ 1.2	2.1 $\pm$ 0.8	< 0.05
TNF- α (pg/mL)	9.5 $\pm$ 3.1	5.2 $\pm$ 2.4	< 0.05
IL-6 (pg/mL)	7.1 $\pm$ 2.8	3.9 $\pm$ 1.9	< 0.05

The table compares pre- and post-supplementation levels for inflammatory markers, such as hs-CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6. A substantial decrease ($p < 0.05$) in all three markers was seen following four months of vitamin D treatment, demonstrating reduced systemic inflammation.

Table 2: Changes in Oxidative Stress Markers Before and After Vitamin D Supplementation

Oxidative Stress Markers	Baseline (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Post-Supplementation (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
TAC (mmol/L)	0.87 $\pm$ 0.20	1.32 $\pm$ 0.35	< 0.05
MDA (nmol/mL)	4.3 $\pm$ 1.1	2.7 $\pm$ 0.9	< 0.05
GPx (U/L)	52.8 $\pm$ 13.5	74.6 $\pm$ 19.8	< 0.05

Vitamin D supplementation affects total antioxidant capacity (TAC), malondialdehyde (MDA), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx). TAC and GPx activity improved significantly ($p < 0.05$), and MDA levels decreased, indicating reduced oxidative stress.

Table 3: Vitamin D Levels Before and After Supplementation

Parameter	Baseline (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Post-Supplementation (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
Serum 25(OH)D (ng/mL)	18.4 $\pm$ 5.9	38.2 $\pm$ 6.7	< 0.001

This table compares pre- and post-intervention serum 25(OH)D levels. Supplementation led to a considerable rise ($p < 0.001$) in vitamin D levels, proving its efficiency in treating deficiency.

Table 4: Hormonal and Reproductive Changes

Hormonal Parameters	Baseline (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Post-Supplementation (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
LH (IU/L)	12.7 $\pm$ 4.8	8.6 $\pm$ 3.1	< 0.05
FSH (IU/L)	5.8 $\pm$ 2.1	5.6 $\pm$ 1.9	> 0.05
LH/FSH Ratio	2.2 $\pm$ 0.9	1.5 $\pm$ 0.6	< 0.05
Testosterone (ng/dL)	72.4 $\pm$ 18.9	56.1 $\pm$ 14.3	< 0.05
Menstrual Regularity (%)	40%	78%	-
Ovulation Rate (%)	30%	55%	-

This table shows participant hormonal and reproductive outcomes. Significant decreases in LH, LH/FSH ratio, and testosterone levels were observed ($p < 0.05$). Period regularity improved from 40% baseline to 78% post-intervention, as did ovulation rates. Despite not being statistically significant, ovulation rates rose from 30% to 55%.

Discussion

This study showed that infertile women with polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) benefit from vitamin D treatment in terms of decreased inflammation, oxidative stress, and improved hormonal balance [9]. The noteworthy alterations noted in markers of oxidative and inflammatory stress indicate that vitamin D is essential for reducing the metabolic disruptions connected to PCOS, which are frequently connected to infertility and other problems in reproductive health [10]. The study's main discovery was the substantial decrease in inflammatory markers, such as hs-CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6, after vitamin D administration. It is generally known that women with PCOS experience chronic low-grade inflammation, which exacerbates insulin resistance, ovarian dysfunction, and unfavorable reproductive outcomes [11]. This observed decline in inflammatory markers is consistent with other research highlighting the anti-inflammatory properties of vitamin D, which is known to regulate immune responses and prevent the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. This shows that taking supplements of vitamin D may be a useful tactic to reduce inflammation in PCOS, therefore enhancing ovarian health and fertility [12].

Improvements in TAC, MDA, and GPx activity showed that vitamin D treatment also dramatically reduced oxidative stress, another important component in the pathogenesis of PCOS. In PCOS, oxidative stress plays a role in anovulation, decreased folliculogenesis, and insulin resistance

[13]. The body's antioxidant defences are strengthened by vitamin D, which lowers oxidative damage. This is demonstrated by the rise in total antioxidant capacity and the fall in lipid peroxidation (as determined by MDA). This supports the theory that vitamin D is an antioxidant that shield cells from oxidative damage and enhance metabolic health in PCOS-affected women [14]. The study demonstrated beneficial benefits on hormonal balance and reproductive outcomes, in addition to inflammation and oxidative stress. Significant drops in testosterone, LH, and the LH/FSH ratio were noted, which may indicate that the hormonal imbalance that defines PCOS has returned. PCOS is characterized by elevated LH and LH/FSH ratios, which are linked to ovarian dysfunction and anovulation [15]. Vitamin D may help normalize menstrual periods and enhance ovarian responsiveness by reducing these levels. In addition, the study discovered that supplementation increased ovulation and menstrual regularity, providing more evidence for vitamin D's beneficial effects on reproductive health. Even while the rise in ovulation rates wasn't statistically significant in every instance, the pattern suggests that, with more intervention, reproductive outcomes may improve [16].

Vitamin D reduces inflammation, oxidative stress, and hormonal control in PCOS women through many pathways. Vitamin D receptors are found in the ovaries, immunological cells, and adipose tissue, affecting metabolic and endocrine activities [17]. Vitamin D may regulate inflammation and oxidative stress genes by binding to these receptors, reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines and reactive oxygen species. Vitamin D's effects on calcium metabolism and insulin sensitivity may indirectly improve ovarian function by improving glucose homeostasis along with decreasing insulin resistance in PCOS patients [18].

Vitamin D improves inflammation, oxidative stress, and reproductive outcomes in PCOS, as shown by previous research. Studies reveal that vitamin D insufficiency is common in PCOS women and is linked to metabolic and reproductive issues [19]. Our study highlights how focused vitamin D supplementation improves inflammation, oxidative stress, and hormonal balance, adding to this expanding body of evidence. The findings are promising, but larger trials with longer follow-up periods are required to validate vitamin D's long-term advantages in PCOS management and fertility [20].

Despite promising results, this study had limitations. While 100 participants are sufficient to identify significant changes in important markers, the findings may not be generalizable. Four-month research may not have been long enough to observe longer-term reproductive outcomes like pregnancy and live birth rates. Extending the intervention duration and integrating these clinical outcomes may assist future research. We lacked a control group to enhance our causal inferences about vitamin D supplementation. This study shows that vitamin D administration lowers inflammation, oxidative stress, hormonal imbalance, and reproductive health in infertile PCOS women. Given the significant incidence of vitamin D deficiency in this group, vitamin D therapy may enhance metabolic and reproductive outcomes with minimal expense. Larger trials should validate these findings and examine vitamin D's long-term impact on fertility and conception in PCOS women.

Conclusion

This study showed that giving infertile women with polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) vitamin D supplements dramatically lowers inflammation and oxidative stress while enhancing hormonal balance. The improvement of oxidative stress indices and the decrease in inflammatory markers including hs-CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6 suggest that vitamin D is essential in reducing the metabolic abnormalities linked to PCOS. Furthermore, the improvements in ovulation rates and monthly regularity imply that vitamin D may improve reproductive health in women with PCOS-related infertility. These results highlight vitamin D's potential as a therapeutic intervention for PCOS and its associated problems. To validate these findings and determine the long-term effects of vitamin D on fertility outcomes, more investigation is needed.

References

1. Al-Shoumer KA, Al-Essa TM. Serum levels of 25-hydroxyvitamin D in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Saudi Med J*. 2015;36 (4):477-83.
2. Holick MF. Vitamin D deficiency. *N Engl J Med*. 2007;357(3):266-81.

3. Wehr E, Pilz S, Boehm BO, März W, Obermayer-Pietsch B. Association of hypovitaminosis D with metabolic disturbances in polycystic ovary syndrome. *Eur J Endocrinol*. 2009;161(4):575-82.
4. Pal L, Berry A, Coraluzzi L, Kustanovich M, Danton C, Shaw J, et al. Therapeutic implications of vitamin D and calcium in overweight women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Gynecol Endocrinol*. 2012;28(12):965-8.
5. Muscogiuri G, Policola C, Prioletta A, Sorice GP, Mezza T, Lassandro AP, et al. Low levels of 25(OH)D and insulin-resistance: 2 unrelated features or a cause-effect in PCOS?. *Clin Nutr*. 2012;31(4):476-80.
6. Selimoglu H, Duran C, Kiyici S, Ersoy R, Guclu M, Tatar G. The effect of vitamin D replacement on insulin resistance and androgen levels in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *J Endocrinol Invest*. 2010;33(4):234-8.
7. Yildizhan R, Kurdoglu M, Adali E, Kulusari A, Edirne T, Sahin HG, et al. Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D concentrations in obese and non-obese women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Arch Gynecol Obstet*. 2009;280(4): 55 9-63.
8. Voulgaris N, Papanastasiou L, Piaditis G, Angelousi A, Kaltsas G, Mastorakos G, et al. Vitamin D and aspects of female fertility. *Hormones (Athens)*. 2017;16(1):5-21.
9. Dastorani M, Aghadavod E, Khalkhali HR, Zarei S, Asemi Z. Magnesium and vitamin D co-supplementation affects glucose homeostasis and markers of cardio-metabolic risk in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2018;184(2):300-7.
10. Thys-Jacobs S, Donovan D, Papadopoulos A, Sarrel P, Bilezikian JP. Vitamin D and calcium dysregulation in the polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Steroids*. 1999;64(6):430-5.
11. Lerchbaum E, Obermayer-Pietsch B. Vitamin D and fertility: a systematic review. *Eur J Endocrinol*. 2012;166(5):765-78.
12. Krul-Poel YH, Koenders PP, Steegers-Theunissen RP, ten Boekel E, Wee MM, Feskens EJ, et al. Vitamin D and metabolic disturbances in polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS): A cross-sectional study. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(12)
13. Pal L, Zhang H, Williams J, Santoro N, Diamond MP, Schlaff WD, et al. Vitamin D status relates to reproductive outcome in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: secondary analysis of a randomized controlled trial. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2016;101(8):3027-35.
14. Asemi Z, Esmailzadeh A. Effects of vitamin D and calcium supplementation on inflammation and oxidative stress in gestational diabetes: a randomized double-blind placebo-

- controlled clinical trial. *Diabetologia*. 2015;58(12):2368-76.
15. Mirhosseini N, Vatanparast H, Mazidi M, Kimball SM. The effect of improved serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D status on glycemic control in diabetic patients: a meta-analysis. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2017;102(9):3097-110.
 16. Haq A, Svobodová J, Imran S, Stanford C, Razzaque MS. Vitamin D deficiency: A single centre analysis of patients from 136 countries. *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol*. 2016;164:209-13.
 17. Trummer C, Schwetz V, Kollmann M, Wölfler MM, Münzker J, Giuliani A, et al. Effects of vitamin D supplementation on metabolic and endocrine parameters in PCOS: A randomized-controlled trial. *Eur J Nutr*. 2019;58(5):2019-28.
 18. Rafiq S, Jeppesen PB. Is hypovitaminosis D related to cardiometabolic risk factors in polycystic ovary syndrome? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutr Res*. 2018;47:9-18.
 19. He C, Lin Z, Robb SW, Ezeamama AE. Serum vitamin D levels and polycystic ovary syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutrients*. 2015;7(6):4555-77.
 20. Rashidi H, Tehranian N, Pirjani R, Sepidarkish M, Hosseini S, Salehpour S. The effects of vitamin D supplementation on metabolic profiles and oxidative stress in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: A randomized placebo-controlled trial. *J Endocrinol Invest*. 2019;42(3):281-9.